

NEW DESIGN FOR AN ORNITHOPTER DRONE USING SIMPLE MECHANISM BASED ON PID CONTROLLERE**Zouaoui SATLA****ORCID: 0000-0003-1142-4194****Kouider BENDINE****ORCID: 0000-0003-1842-5157****Mohamed ELAJRAMI****ORCID: 0000-0003-0928-6124****Lakhdar BOUMIA****ORCID:0000-0002-7693-7081****ABSTRACT**

The present paper presents a new design of an unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) called ZK0.1, which is an ornithopter. The design uses a simple mechanism with three driving engines to control the wings' movement. The full model was designed in SOLIDWORKS and then exported to MATLAB using SIMMECHANICS interface to add control blocks. A PID controller was implemented and added to the identified blocks to monitor the ZK0.1. The PID parameters were defined using a tuning tool provided by MATLAB. The simulations showed promising results, indicating that the proposed model can be used widely due to its ease of controlling and simple driving mechanism. Thorough, the paper provides a comprehensive approach to designing and controlling a UAV with a novel ornithopter design, demonstrating the potential for further exploration and development in this area.

Keywords: UAV, ornithopter, ZK0.1, solidworks, matlab/simulink, Simmechanics, PID controls.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, drones have been widely integrated in all sectors of mankind life. It can be found in every daily routine and served in a huge number of applications starting from the advance military tasks to a small playing tool in the hand of the children. This versatility is going even deeper as more applications have located especially in the time of Covid-19 epidemic which has set a new role such as sterilization, protection, monitoring of epidemic hotspots and providing medical and food supply. Due to the reasons mentioned previously, the drones design and developments have become a hot topic and many researchers (Satla, Z) are focusing on providing more reliable designed that can be easy to monitor and construct. (S. Zouaoui et al, 2018), (E. Mohamed et all, 2021), proposed a simple model to determine the path and the deriving control parameters using genetic algorithm for the case of drones. Additionally (S. Róbert, 2020), investigated the path of low-flying aircraft. A review work for different drone applications in smart cities can be found in (N.D. Dung, 2021).

In the upcoming future, drones can be a presented as alternative replacement that can be used in different industrial and privet applications, especially fields related to delivering service, rescues or even farming. What created an open field for research and development and the purification of several types that were touched upon and collected most of them in study (S. Darvishpoor et all, 2020) that included biological drones called ornithopter. An ornithopter (from the Greek ornis, ornith- "bird" and pteron "wing") is a drone that flies by flapping its wings. Designers have always been looking for a model that can replace the wing-flapping flight of birds, bats and insects. As for bio-mechanical aircraft, the authors have noticed a lack of researches which can be explained by the modeling challenges compared to other types. However, there are researches that are concerned with these types, such as (Y.W. Chin et all, 2020) Although ornithopter machines may be different

in shape, they are usually made to the same level as flying animals. Larger helicopters were also built, some of which were successful to a large extent and some of them were able to achieve the quality of bird flight. However, there are always difficulties and challenges, including control, structure and mechanism parts design.

Recent research focused on the trajectory of an aircraft, Trajectory optimization has recently been addressed to compute energy-efficient routes for ornithopter navigation (Pérez-Cutiño et al., 2022) this paper presents algorithms that recursively generate trajectories based on the output of neural networks and random forest, when the authors create a large data set composed by energy-efficient trajectories obtained by running a competitive planner. Authors in the mentioned paper claimed that their work was the first of its kind that contains a large number of near-optimal pathways for ornithopter pathway improvement, which helps implementing three methods to calculate low-cost paths: two classification approaches for learning maneuvers and an alternative regression method that predicts new states. The algorithms are tested in several scenarios, including the landing case. The effectiveness and efficiency of the proposed algorithms are demonstrated through simulation. Another research has been studied (Rodríguez. F et al., 2022) An optimization of trajectory has recently been addressed to compute energy-efficient routes for ornithopter navigation. To overcome the high computation time of habitual approaches However, various techniques of control were tested to plan energy-efficient trajectories for autonomous ornithopters in this research.

There is some research interested in design and construction UAV ornithopter, (Md. Nazmul Hasan et al., 2016) has been suggested new model and development which flaps its wings in fixed amplitude with variable frequencies. A crank shaft mechanism was introduced to make the wings in good movement. The model was motorized by a 100 watt DC motor with necessary gearbox assemblies. The controlling and maneuvering have been done by a radio communication and bird like tail consequently. 3 channel radio communications was needed to control the flapping frequency and tail combinations. Flying upward, downward, left, right and 360 degree rolling is possible with this tail combination. Micro servo motors were used for tail mechanism. Design and Construction of an Autonomous Ornithopter are considered (J. Grauer and J. Hubbard, 2010), for better study the control of flapping wing flight the authors have developed a large scale ornithopter called the Phoenix. It is capable of carrying a heavy (400 gram) computer and sensor package and is designed especially for the application of controls research; this type has been developed and studied of both the mechanical and electrical systems of the ornithopter and initial control experiments. The drone was Exposed it to stabilize the mechanism in pitch with a simple PD controller from beginning to end experimental testing.

However, flight dynamics for state estimation and control modeling of ornithopter are discussed (Jackowski, Z.J., 2009) , nonlinear multibody model of the ornithopter flight dynamics, has been guided by flight tests and system identification results, and cast into a canonical form for nonlinear control. A simulation of trimmed flight and pitch rate damping was presented, viewing promise for more advanced control algorithms. Adaptive Nonlinear Control for perching of a bioinspired ornithopter are approached (F. J. Maldonado et al., 2020) Researchers in this area presented a nonlinear controller for an ornithopter model with bioinspired wings and tail. The size and power requirements have been thought to allocate a customized autopilot on board. To evaluate the functionality and performance of the full mechatronic design, a controller has been designed and implemented to execute a prescribed perching 2D trajectory. In addition to all these research and articles, there are many researchers who have differed interest in ornithopter. There are those who are interested in designing and there are those who focus on the control algorithms of this type of drones, as well its applications in various fields. And the failure of this field to reach its role in research makes those wishing to develop these drones interested in achieving and inventing new types with satisfaction. For this purpose, this type of aircraft has been studied in this research.

In this Paper, a new type of drone ornithopter named as ZK0.1 is proposed. The design is made to be simple and easy which helps the monitoring and the fabrication of the drone. A simple PID controller is used to

monitor the ZK0.1. To allow the numerical simulation, a full model design has been created using Solidworks and exported to MTLAB/Simulink. After that, each block was treated separately to verify the movement of each component part of an aircraft. Then a logically selected type is processed by following the movement and flight of the birds, where the structure is flown and raised with a wings movement and directed with a vertical movement of Tail up and down, while a lateral movement of ornithopter is done by rotating of Tail right and left. And in order to ensure every movement, a motor is harnessed to move the wings and tow servo-motors to guide the tail one for right / left and the other for up /down.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: In Section 2, we present a description of The ZK0.1 model including the principal physical, kinematics and dynamics flight mechanical. Section 3 discusses the fundamentals of PID controller after using interface between Solidworks and Matlab/Simulink. In Section 4 we deliver the fundamentals simulation results of present paper. Section 5 present comprehensible conclusion which includes the outcomes of the paper.

MODEL DESCRIPTIONS

The biggest challenge of flapping wing ornithopter design remains the integration of relatively complex flapping and control mechanisms into a small and lightweight package that can be lifted by the thrust produced, in order to improve its pilots and make them more efficient and approximate the movements of a real bird.

The proposed design consists of three main engines one located in the center of the model; this last is transferring a rotation movement to the mechanism actuator that shifts the wings. The mechanism is mainly used to transfer the rotation movement to a translation based with the help of Gear-shaft principle. The second and the third engines are located in the tail, their role is to rotate the tail up and down and right and left.

The complete design is implemented in Solidworks and detailed in Figs 1 and 2. There is a third engine shown in the Fig 2, which was ignored in this study (servo 3) It will be taken into consideration in a future work related to field experience, and it is related to the inclination of the wings to increase steering during flight.

Figure 1: The proposed design configuration of the ZK0.1.

Figure 2: The driven kinematics and flight dynamics of the ZK0.1.

PID CONTROLLER

In order to simulate the proposed model with new mechanism design depicted in Fig 3, the design is exported to Matlab/Simulink via Simmechanics module. The transferring phase results a block diagram presentation contains all the parts and the driven movement as presented in Fig. 4 and Fig 5 with subsystems blocks.

Figure 3 : mechanism design of oriohpter.

To be able control the model in Simulink, it is required to add a controller. The control algorithm is the brain that serves to monitor and control the model movements and also ensure the safe flight Fig.5.

Figure 4: ZK0.1 ornithopter model dynamics.

A model was chosen for both the Motor (equation 01) and the Servos (equation 02), as shown in two transfer functions, respectively:

$$F_{motor} = \frac{0.0274}{8.878e^{-12} * s^2 + 1.291e^{-05} * s + 7.648e^{-04}} \quad (01)$$

$$F_{servo} = \frac{19.375}{s + 3.975} \quad (02)$$

Figure 5: ZK0.1 Ornithopter model with subsystems blocks.

After extracting a model in Matlab and starting a simulation show in Figure 6, it was confirmed that there was a match between the SolidWorks (figure 01) and Matlab models, and this confirms the process of converting a model to another stage. The next step is to confirm. It is the integration of a controller in order to study the behavior of an aircraft during a simulation in addition to correcting errors caused by a change in its flight direction. In our case a PID controller (Satla.Z, et all 2019) have choose due to its reliability and easy and simple configuration.

Figure 6: The ornithopter ZK0.1 in Matlab environment.

The control input u used to control the speed of motor and angles of servos and position of wings of the drone respect to the reference input designed as follows (Satla.Z, et all 2019):

$$u(t) = K_p e(t) + K_i \int e(t) dt + K_d \dot{e}(t). \quad (03)$$

K_p : is the proportional gain;

K_i : is the integral gain;

And K_d : is the derivation gain.

With error can be formulated as:

$$e(t) = s_p - p_v(t) \quad (3)$$

s_p : is the setpoint or desired position.

And $p_v(t)$: is the process variable at instantaneous time according to s_p . A high-quality controller must be able to establish a desired position. By using transfer function for motor, servo 01 and servo 02.

The controller block can be found in Fig. 7 while the mathematical description is given in the previous paragraph.

Figure 7: blocks schema with including the PID controllers.

The following table 01 shows the selected values of the PID controller, in order to get the best response in the shortest time.

Table 1 Chosen values of the PID controller.

CONTROLLER PARAMETER	KP	Kİ	KD
MOTOR	3.5	9	2
SERVO 01	7	18	5.5
SERVO 02	2.5	5.5	2

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The variations on the rotation of motor and movement of servo 01, with servo 02 responses over times are presented in Fig. 8, Fig. 9, and Fig. 10 respectively, the curves show that the ZK0.1 is attempted the desire movement which prove the accuracy of the present controller.

Figure 8: Motor response.

Figure 9: Servo 01 response Responsible for first angle 1 control.

Figure10: Servo 02 response Responsible for first angle 2 control.

In addition, some undesirable behaviors were observed at the beginning of the simulation, especially with regard to the tail angle control as show in Figure 11, which is very normal because the initial position of the tail was at the start of the simulation not coinciding (parallelism) the desired angle starting point at the beginning of the curve after which they coincide after a short time. Notice after a second the stability of simulation and stability of the design. With respect to the tail angle (right-left) there is stability with a somewhat noticeable line. This is due to its association with the angle (fall and descent), but it was not taken into account in this preliminary study

Figure 11: Errors of angle1 (vertical angle) and angle 2 (tail angle).

CONCLUSION

The paper in question explores the modeling, stabilization, and control of a small uav ornithopter. The authors begin by designing the model zk0.1 in solidworks, a computer-aided design software commonly used in engineering and architecture. Once the design is completed, the model is coupled with a proportional-integral-derivative (pid) control algorithm schema to simulate its dynamic behavior after export to matlab simscape model.

The simulation results show that the error between the required path and the simulation is very low for the two control angles. However, the control of the second servomotor is not as stable as the first servomotor due to the ignored link relation with servomotor 01. This is because the study is a preliminary exploration of the new and innovative design, and further research is needed to fully optimize the model.

Although this issue, the proposed model is proven to be stable and durable. The study demonstrates that the ornithopter is capable of maintaining its suggested track, even when subjected to various disturbances. The authors conclude that future works should focus on improving the design by adding enhancements to the wings and controlling parameters using optimization algorithms.

The paper provides valuable insights into the technical and practical considerations involved in the design and control of ornithopter drones. The study highlights the importance of understanding the link relations between servomotors and the role of pid control algorithms in stabilizing the model. The authors also emphasize the need for experimental validation of the simulation results to confirm the conservative outcomes of this preliminary study.

In conclusion, the research paper presents a comprehensive investigation into the modeling, stabilization, and control of a small uav ornithopter. The study provides a solid foundation for further research and development of ornithopter drones and serves as a valuable reference for engineers and researchers in the field.

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